

A CASE STUDY ON AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF (SCIATICA) *GHRIDHRASI**¹Dr. Sumit Ramchandra Dhengle, ²Dr. Vandana Avhad¹MD Scholar Panchkarma, Sumatibhaishah Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Hadapsar, Pune.²MD Panchakarma, PhD Panchakarma, Associate Professor Department of Panchakarma, Sumatibhaishah Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Hadapsar, Pune.

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ABSTRACT

The lower back pain is one of the commonest complaints most practitioner encounter with. Pain may be acute or chronic. The position of pain itself indicates sciatica. Generally it's most common condition causes low back pain radiating in posterior part of legs. Sciatica resembles *Ghridhrasi* mentioned in Classical Ayurvedic texts in *Vataja Nanatamaja Vikara*.^[1] Almost 50% of people experiences pain at some point in life.^[2] In *Ghridhrasi* pain starts from *Kati Prushtha* (pelvic and lumbo sacral region) towards *Jangha Pada* (thigh and legs) with *Sthambha* (stiffness). The *Panchakarma* procedure and internal medicine shows remarkable results. Here a case in this article about patient suffering from Sciatic pain (radiating downwards from right lumbar region to foot) mild narrow space changes seen in Xray, but clinically patient had signs and symptoms. Patient was treated with course of *Snigdha Sankar Sweda* and later after 7 days internal medicine were given. Patient showed remarkable improvement and can do daily work easily.

KEYWORDS: Sciatica, *Ghridhrasi*, *Panchakarma*, *Swedana*.**INTRODUCTION**

Sciatica can occur suddenly or gradually. The symptoms of a “pinched nerve” affects one or more spinal nerves. Pinched nerve can be inside or outside of spinal canal as passes into legs. The pain refers to pricking sensations, stiffness along the path of Sciatic nerve, tingling numbness etc. Now a days incidence of Sciatic pain also seen in younger population also, though men are more affected than women. The name *Ghridhrasi* itself resembles *Ghridhra* (*Vulture*).^[3] The walk of *Ghridhra* relates to disease sign. It is included in 80 types of *Nanatamaja Vata Vikara*. *Ghridhrasi* divided into *Vataja* and *Vata – Kaphaja*.^[4] The *Keval Vataja* shows pain with pricking sensations, stiffness and repeated twitching in buttock, low back pain, thigh, back of knee, calf, foot. In *Vata Kaphaja*^[5] shows feeling of heaviness, drowsiness and anorexia presence. Sciatica mainly treated as *Vata Vyadhi*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS**A case study**

A 36 year old Male comes in OPD of *Panchakarma* Department with signs and symptoms of Sciatica.

Chief clinical complaints

- 1) Severe pain in low back and radiating towards calf and down to foot.
- 2) Stiffness in Lumbar region.
- 3) Bloating.
- 4) Dryness in hand and foot.

Since 2 months

History of past illness

K/C/O- No any known

S/H/O- No any known

General Examination

O/E – BP -130/90mmhg

Pulse-76/min

Wt-68 kg

Asthavidh pariksha

Nadi - Vatapradhan Pitta	Shabda- Spashta
Mala - Asamyaka	Sparsha - Samshitoshana
Mutra - Samayaka	Druka - Spashta
Jivha - Ishat Sama	Akruti - Madhyam

Neurological Examination

Tests	Right leg	Left leg
SLRT	30°	Negative

Assessment criteria

1) Low back pain radiating down to foot	G ₀	Pain in Lumbar region not radiated.
	G ₁	Pain in Lumbar region radiated in thigh.
	G ₂	Pain in Lumbar region radiated in calf.
	G ₃	Pain in Lumbar region radiated in foot.

2) Stiffness in Lumbar region	G ₀	No Stiffness
	G ₁	Mild Stiffness
	G ₂	Moderate Stiffness
	G ₃	Severe Stiffness

3) Difficulty and Pain in walking and sitting	G ₀	No Pain
	G ₁	Mild + No difficulty in walking and sitting
	G ₂	Slight difficulty in walking and sitting
	G ₃	Much difficulty in walking and sitting

Nidana Panchak

1) Nidana

Heavy weight lifting, Prolonged standing, Atichakramana.

2) Poorvaroop

Pain and Stiffness in lumbar and lower back region.

3) Roopa

Pain in lumbar region, radiating towards thigh, calf and down to foot, difficulty in walking and sitting.

4) Samprapti

Hetu Sevana vitiated Vatadosha due to excess walk, prolonged standing and heavy weight lifting. Vitiated Vatadosha increase in Rukshata, Kharata and vitiated Kaphadosha increased in Stambha in lumbar vertebrae leads to decrease in elasticity and flexibility of the disc decrease functioning of joints in Lumbar region. Mild compression of nerve i.e. Prakshobha of Vatavahini Nadi. Nerve compression cause low back pain, gluteal, calf in Right leg.

5) Upshaya Anupshaya

Upshaya by Snigdha Sankar Sweda.

Investigation

X-ray - Mild narrowing in space in Lumbar vertebrae and Paraspinal muscle spasm seen.

Chikitsa

Swedana^[6] and internal medicine after 7 days According to Acharya Sushruta and Acharya Vagbhata both mentioned the Snehana, Swedana Chikitsa in basic management of all Vatavyadhis.

Treatment plan

According to Acharya Charaka, Patra Pinda Sweda a type Snigdha Sankar Sweda^[7] - By Nirgundi Patra^[8] + Til Taila from Right lumbar region to right foot and internal medicine after 7 days of Swedana treatment.

Details of Treatment

Poorvakarma - Nirgundi Patra Bharjana with Til Taila and Pottali is made. Snehana by Til Taila from Right lumbar region to right foot.

Pradhanakarma - Snigdha Sankar Sweda by Nirgundi Patra Pottali from Right lumbar region to foot in Anulomana Gati, on joints Swedana done in circular motion for 20 mins.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Complaints	Before treatment	After treatment
1) Low back pain radiating down to foot	G ₃	G ₀
2) Stiffness in Lumbar region	G ₂	G ₁
3) Difficulty and Pain while walking and sitting	G ₂	G ₀
4) SLRT	30°	60°

DISCUSSION

In this case study we treated patient by *Snigdha Sankar Sweda* with *Nirgundi Patra* and *Til Taila*. *Nirgundi Patra* have *Katu, Tikta, Kashaya Rasa, Katu Vipaka, Ushna Veerya, Ruksha, Laghu Guna* does the *Kapha Pachana* and relieves in *Sthambha Lakshana* and *Til Taila* have *Madhur Rasa, Madhur Vipaka, Ushna Veerya, Snigdha Guna* does the *Vata Shamana*. After 7 days of treatment 70% improvement seen in his complaints of pain and stiffness.

CONCLUSION

In this treatment of *Ghridhrasi* by giving *Sthanik Snigdha Sankar Sweda*, as it is one of the *Nanatamaja Vata Vikara*, but here *Vata Kaphaja Prakara* diagnosis mandates to *Kapha Pachana* by *Swedana* and *Upshaya* is gained.

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